

Maintenance of Healthy Lifestyle with special reference to *Sūtra Sthāna* of *Charaka Saṃhitā*

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Abstract: India is a beautiful and vast country enriched with unique culture, glorious tradition and ambrosia of knowledge. Ancient India is augmented with distinctive sacred scriptures like Vedas, Upaniṣads, purāṇas, Bhagavad Gīta, Rāmāyaṇa, Mahābhārata, Bible, Quran, Yogasūtra of Patanjali, Dharmasāstra etc. Amidst these four Vedas like Rigveda (knowledge of the hymns of praise), Sāmaveda (knowledge of the melodies), Yajurveda (knowledge of the sacrificial formulas), and Atharvaveda (knowledge of the magic formulas) are exclusive Hindu sacred scriptures. The original source of Āyurveda is ascribed to Atharvaveda where discussion is made on several diseases with their treatments. The Charaka Saṃhitā is a famous book of antique medical treatises based on Āyurveda. We know that 'śarīramādyam khaludharmasādhanam'. It means our body is the main point of focus for the performance of our duty properly. Our body and mind are the basic sources to get caturbarga. So the care and safeguard of them should be very essential. The diet plays a very crucial role which has direct impact on three doṣas. If we maintain our diet in a balanced way then these three doṣas get balanced. Balanced diet provides us complexion, longevity, brilliancy, pleasure, satisfaction, nourishment, vigour, energy, etc. The diet that contains all the nutrients in a proper amount and nourishes both the mental and physical built is called balanced diet. Apart from diet there are several other factors like oral hygiene, personal hygiene, proper sleep etc. which are responsible for healthy lifestyle. This paper focuses mainly on the factors behind healthy lifestyle, their maintenance and to some extent their present relevance.

Keywords: Balanced diet, diseases, happiness, hygiene, longevity, lifestyle.

Introduction:

The *Charaka Saṃhitā* is one of the most important and authentic foundational Sanskrit textbook of the medical tradition in ancient India based on *Āyurveda* and also one among the three of the *bṛhatrayi* whose literal meaning is 'The three great ancient Sanskrit encyclopaedias of medicine'. The books are the *Charaka Saṃhitā* by Charaka, the *Suśruta Saṃhitā* by Suśruta and the *Aṣṭāṅghṛday saṃhitā* by Vagbhata. The *Āyurveda* means *āyur anena bindati betti vā Āyurvedaḥ*. This word is derived from *āyus* and the root *bid* with instrumental *ghañ* suffix. The word *āyus* means 'life' or 'longevity' and *Veda* means 'knowledge'. So *Āyurveda* means knowledge of life and longevity. It is also called as the science of life (Swain, 2012). The origin of *Āyurveda* is from *Atharva Veda* where several diseases with their treatments have been mentioned. *Atharva Veda* is the fourth *Veda* amongst four Vedas. *Charaka Saṃhitā* is the review of *Agniveśa Saṃhitā* composed by Agniveśa. It defines *Āyurveda* in the following manner—

"hitahitam sukhamdukham āyustasya hitāhitam|
mānamca tacca yatrotam āyurvedaḥ sa ucyate||"
(*Charaka Saṃhitā*, *Sūtra Sthāna*, Ch.1, Ver.41)

It means *Āyurveda* explains and provides treatment methods for beneficial life, harmful life, joyful state of health and mind, miserable state of health and mind. *Charaka Saṃhitā* consists of 120 chapters in eight specific *Sthānas* such as, *Sūtra Sthāna*, *Nidāna Sthāna*, *Vimāna Sthāna*, *Śarīra Sthāna*, *Indriya Sthāna*, *Chikitsā Sthāna*, *Kalpa Sthāna*, *Siddhi Sthāna*. The first part is *Sūtra Sthāna* where

the basic principles of longevity are explained (Acharya, 2000).

As we know that everyone is very careful and conscious about his/her own health nowadays. The first basic rule in the maintenance of a healthy life is diet. Healthy food and proper lifestyle is essential for maintaining good health. Due to sedentary lifestyle and diet people are facing various health issues like obesity, type 2 diabetes, some types of cancer, cardiovascular disease, high blood pressure, high cholesterol etc. In this context, several ancient medical textual treasures are providing us innumerable sources (knowledge like nectar) for living a long and healthy life. *Charaka Saṃhitā* is one amongst them. We can get the importance of health in verse no. 15 of *Sūtra Sthāna* (Vidyalankara, 2002):

dharmārthakāmamokṣānām ārogyaṃmōlamuttamam ||
rogāstasyāpahartāraḥ śreyaso jīvitasyaca ||

(*Charaka Saṃhitā, Sūtra Sthāna, Chapter 1, Ver. no.15, 16*)

It means health is the best resource of virtue, prosperity and indulgence while on the other hand diseases are destroyers of this welfare and life itself. To overcome from these great obstacles for human beings these ancient medical texts supply us virtuous knowledge regarding this domain (Loon, 2003). The body and mind are the fundamental source of happiness and disease. So, balanced utilization of time, mental faculties, and object of sense organs are the basis for happiness and vice versa. Regular exercise, balanced diet, and sufficient rest all induced to good health.

Factors involving the Maintenance of Healthy Lifestyle:

Balanced Diet: A diet containing right quantities of nutrients is called a balanced diet. The role of proper diet we take both in quality and quantity is more vital. The quantity of food to be taken depends upon a number of factors like the age of the individual, the season, the power of digestion and metabolism etc. as mentioned in verse no.3 of chapter 5-“*āhāramātrā punaragnibalāpeṣiṇī*” || We should be also regular about meal timings. One should take light foods like *mudga*, common Quail, graypartridge, antelope, rabbit, wapiti, Indian sambar, etc. in proper amount. On the other hand, heavy foods like sugarcane, milk, *tila*(sesamum), *māṣa*, meats of marsy and aquatic animals are also required to be taken in right measurement. Thus, if taken in excessive quantity they are definitely very harmful. Their harmfulness can be neutralized only when there is a corresponding stronger digestive power caused by the physical exercise. It is also mentioned in ver.7, ch.5 that if the food is heavy then, only three fourth or half of the stomach capacity is to be filled up. In the case light food excessive intake is not conducive to the maintenance of the power of digestion and metabolism. So food taken in appropriate quantity brings strength, complexion, happiness and longevity. Regular intake of heavy food such as *vallōra* (dried meat), dry vegetables, *kōrcikā* (boiled buttermilk), *kilāṭa* (inspissated milk), pork, beef, meat of buffalo, fish, curd, *māṣa* (phaseolus radiates Linn.), *yavaka* (a variety of *Hordeumvulgare* Linn.), lotus rhizomes and lotus stalk is not beneficial for the body. A person should never take meat of a diseased animal. Proper digestion depends upon the proper diet. We should regularly take such food articles that are conducive to the maintenance of good health and are capable of preventing the attacks of diseases in future.

Personal hygiene: Hygiene means avoiding the increase of infectious diseases and directing long and healthy lives. Personal hygiene is the implementations that people defend their health and stay their life well. It means the body, hair, mouth, and teeth must be cleaned on a regular basis and clothes must be washed

repeatedly. Many diseases expand due to lack of hygiene; microbes easily raise in unclean bodies and cause sickness. Regarding personal hygiene, it is told in *Charaka Samhitā* that one should regularly apply the collyrium made of antimony once in every five or eight nights for lacrymation of the eyes (Kaviratna and Sharma). The therapy of collyrium alleviates *kapha* is good for keeping the vision clear. Further, a part of the vitiated *kapha* of the head which is not easily eliminated by the application of collyrium is instantaneously eliminated by smoking. One should smoke sycophantic cigars made of useful drugs of sweet taste along with fat of muscle, ghee, and bee wax in the prescribed method. Smoking by oral route cures heaviness of head, headache, rhinitis hemicranias, earache, pain in eye, cough, hic-cough, dyspnoea, obstruction in throat, weakness of teeth, discharge from the morbid ear, nose and eye, toothache, paleness of face, excessive salivation, impaired voice, tonsillitis, greying and falling of hair sneezing, excessive drowsiness, loss of consciousness, etc. Eight definite times have been provided for regular smoking to avoid diseases from the vitiation of *vāta* and *kapha*. If it is untimely done or overdone, it causes deafness, blindness, dumbness, bleeding from different parts of the body, etc.

We should inhale nasal drop *Anutaila* each year during the three seasons when the sky is free from cloud viz., the rainy season, the autumn and the spring for eradicating the morbid conditions of inter-cellular spaces and channels of the body. One who practices nasal therapy in time as per prescribed method, his eyes, nose and ears are not affected by any morbidity. Diseases like torticollis, headache, facial paralysis, lock jaw, rhinitis, hemicrania and tremors of the head are cured thereby. Being nourished by inhalation, his veins, joints, ligaments and tendons of head and neck get greater strength. At present, allopathic doctor are also prescribing to take vapour of nasal drops for Otorrhea. Oiling of head is also more vital. One who applies *til* oil on his head regularly in sufficient quantity does not suffer from headache, baldness, greying and falling of hair. His hair becomes black, long and deep rooted. Oiling of ears is essential to prevent from ear diseases like torticollis, lock jaw, hardness of hearing and deafness, etc. due to vitiated *vāta*. By the oil massage in the human body it becomes strong, flabby, charming and smooth skinned. Bathing is necessary for purifying. It removes fatigue, sweating and dirt. It provides strength in the body. By wearing clean dress, use of fragrance and use of ornaments brings bodily charm, reputation, prosperity, longevity, pleasure, grace, etc. The dressing and cutting of hair, beard and nails, etc. adds cleanliness, and beauty. The use of foot wears, umbrella, and hand stick give strength, happiness and longevity.

All these things are approved by the physicians nowadays by different forms. We agree with this oldest treasure of ambrosia as there is sufficient scientific logic and authentic truth behind this.

Oral hygiene: Oral hygiene means the practice of keeping our mouth fresh and free of virus. It prevents us from tooth decay and gum diseases. Regarding teeth brushing, it is told in verse no. 71 and 72 of ch.5 that one should use the tooth cleaning stick whose top portion is crushed and is astringent, pungent or bitter in taste like *Karañja*, *Karavīra*, *Arka*, *Mālatī*, *Kakubha*, *Asana*, etc. This removes the foul smell and tastelessness, the dirt of the tongue, teeth and mouth that causing the taste for food. In relation to tongue scraping, it is stated that it should not be sharp edged and are curved, are to be made of metals like gold, silver, copper, tin and brass. The tongue should be scraped regularly to avoid expiration and foul

smell. By chewing the fruits of *jātī*, *kaṭuka*, *pūga*, *kakkola*, *sōkṣmailā*, flower stalk of *lavaṅga*, fresh leaf of *tāmbōla* and the extract of *karpōra*, the good smell of mouth would be maintained. *Til* oil gargling is beneficial for the strength of jaws, depth of voice, and flabbiness of face, excellent gustatory sensation and good taste for food.

Seasonal homologation: The seasonal homologation regarding the regimen and diet, and their effects on the body has been vividly described in ch.6. It is also stated in the verse no. 58 of ch.3, *Sōtra Sthāna* of Aṣṭāṅgaḥṛdaya that one should simultaneously start following up the prescriptions of the succeeding season and the avoidance of those of the preceding season, sometimes between the last week of the preceding season and the first week of the succeeding season (Rao, 2016). There in verse no. 43-44, it is told that the vitiation of *doṣas* is caused by the weakness in the power of digestion during the rains. The factors that cause vitiation of *vāta*, *pitta* and *kapha* are the water vapour coming out of the earth, rain water and the acidity of water. The water vapour coming from the earth vitiates all the three *doṣas*, such as *vāta*, *pitta* and *kapha* due to specific action (Kaviratna & Sharma, 2001). It is relevant at present also. Suppose, if we consume more amount of cold articles during winter and rain definitely we suffer from diseases arising out of them.

Suppression of natural urges: One more thing is that suppression of natural urges like urine, faeces, semen, flatus, vomiting, sneezing, eructation, yawning, hunger, thirst, tears, sleep and breathing are more harmful and give several diseases to our body. It is elaborately narrated in ch.7, *sutra*. of *Cha. Saṃhitā*. For living a normal healthy life, it is necessary that the needs of these natural urges are satisfied instantaneously. Suśruta has explained that by suppressing breathing caused by over exertion one gets heart diseases, fainting or even phantom tumour in the abdomen (*Suśruta, uttaratantra*, 55/17)(Bhishagrajna, 1963). The same concept we get from verse no.24, ch.7 of *Sōtra Sthāna*. It is mentioned in verse no. 31 that physical exercises bring bodily stability and strength are to be practiced moderately. If they are over-done, they cause over-exertion, giddiness etc., that is not desirable. “*śarīraceṣṭāyāceṣṭās-thairyārthābalavardhini*”. It is also stated in verse no. 80, ch. 24, *Cikitsā* of *Suśruta Saṃhitā* (Panigrahi, 2005).

Furthermore, instructions regarding the avoidance of excessive utilization, non-utilization and wrong utilization of sense organs and mind should be followed. Practise regarding taking diet, natural urges, study, self-control, fire worship, social relations, good conduct have been described in ch. 8 of *Sōtra Sthāna*.

Equilibrium of Tridoṣa: In ch.20 it has been mentioned that a person suffers from a disease out of imbalance of *Tridoṣa* namely, *vata*, *pitta* and *kapha*. All the three *doṣas* are present in every part of the body. When they are in normal balanced condition, nourish the body, improve strength and immunity, and provide us good health, but when they are imbalanced due to some reason they cause illness and disorders.

Proper sleep: The role and importance of proper sleep for the maintenance of our body is noticed in ch.21. There it is told that if we have a good sleep, it provides us happiness, nourishment, strength and longevity. So also if we have a disturbed sleep we suffer a lot like misery, weakness, headache, indigestion, drowsiness, etc. So a proper sleep is the basic requirement for a healthy life.

These are all the major factors which are influencing the maintenance of healthy lifestyle according to the *Sōtra Sthāna* of *Charaka Saṃhitā* as well as rele-

vant from the modern point of view. In real life, a layman can also know and understand that if we wake up too late, take our food irregularly as our wish, and take unhealthy foods like fast food, junk food, fatty food, rich and oily food in a huge amount, drink less water, don't get fresh and clean on regular basis, disturbed sleep daily, taking no nutritional food, doing no exercise, then within a very few days we definitely suffer from various harmful diseases. Nobody can rescue us. So, maintaining a healthy lifestyle through nutrition and exercise is very essential for our overall health and well-being. If we avoid junk food and sugary beverages, drink plenty of water, eat food rich in fibre like oats, beans and banana, eat more fresh fruits and green vegetables, and exercise regularly, regular about the meal timings, take a balanced diet then certainly we will enjoy a healthy, wealthy and perfect life.

Conclusion:

The *Charaka Samhitā* is the most fundamental text of the indigenous Indian medical system of *Āyurveda*. *Sōtra Sthāna* of *Charaka Samhitā* recommended briefly all the components of a well- balanced diet like good and fine rice like *Shasti* and *Shali*, *Mudga* (green gram), *Lavana*(salt), *Amalaki* (goose berry), *Yava* (barley), rain water, milk, ghee, flesh of animals living in forests and honey ascertained by modern experts also. The concept of *Nitya Sheelaniya Dravyas* emphasized by both Charaka and Vagbhata clearly indicates the significance of nutrition in daily life. The nutritive value of these *Dravyas* attains the balanced diet criteria which are told by WHO. By consuming of these *dravyas* daily induces to promotion of good health and remove the forthcoming disease condition. Physical well-being necessitates pursuing a healthy lifestyle to reduce the risk of disease. For the maintenance of health, it is essential that a perfect equilibrium is well-established with regard to the various forces acting and counteracting on the body. If there is too much deficiency in any respect anywhere, it is needed to be neutralized. Suppose a place is very cool, the body would regularly require some additional irrelevant heat to maintain itself against the extreme cold of the place. One should try his best to maintain equilibrium with regard to diet, conduct and regimen. Because of this Charaka mentioned that food taken in proper quantity provides strength, complexion, and a happy life. Dietary habits, personal hygiene, oral hygiene, seasonal homologation, suppression of natural urges, equilibrium of *tridoṣa*, and proper sleep are essential for achieving and maintaining overall physical and emotional well-being throughout life. So, we have to follow certain disciplined order according to the prescribed format to become healthy, wealthy, and pleasant and maintain a peaceful life forever.

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